

Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies

ISSN: P-0972-3331 E-2582-8711

Vol 21/1-2 Jan-June 2022 **226-242**

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5722105

Stable URL: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722105>

St Francis of Assisi and *Fratelli Tutti*: A Historical Purview

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Abstract: As humans we are always faced with problems. In this world of problems there have always been persons, who lead the world to reach the other shore. It is in this context of present world that Pope Francis brings out his Encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, with the theme fraternal love and social relationship, a way to live in this world as brothers and sisters. He tells us that in these pages of the Encyclical of reflection on universal fraternity, he is inspired particularly persons of the past like by Saint Francis of Assisi, but also others who are not Catholics, like Martin Luther King,

Cite as: Joseph M.D. (2022). St Francis of Assisi and Fratelli Tutti: A Historical Purview (Version 1.0). *Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies*, Jan-June 2022(26/1-2), **226-242**.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722105>

Desmond Tutu, Mahatma Gandhi and many others. These persons are people who bring hope to the world. The Pope says that he would like to conclude by mentioning another person of great faith. He is blessed Charles de Foucauld. He was a man of intense experience of God, who made a journey of transformation towards feeling a brother to all. It is from this background that this research paper is being brought out titled, “St Francis of Assisi and Fratelli Tutti: A Historical Purview.”

Keywords: Pope Francis, Fratelli Tutti, St Francis of Assisi, Fraternity, Social Relationship.

Introduction

Fraternity and social relationship are the ways, the Holy Father Pope Francis indicates to build a better world by the cooperation and understanding of all peoples and institutions of the world. The Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, deals with the ideals and the tangible ways for all people of good will to build a more just and fraternal world in our ordinary relationships, in social life, politics and institutions. This is what this encyclical tries to convey to us. The holy Father describes it as a universal social encyclical, which borrows the admonitions of Saint Francis of Assisi who used these words to address his brothers and sisters and put forward to them a way of life flavored by the Gospel. The encyclical invites everyone to aspiration towards fraternity and social relationship. It is brought out in the background of the Covid-19 pandemic, which Pope Francis says, unexpectedly erupted as he was writing this letter. It is from this context that this paper is being brought titled, *St Francis Assisi and Fratelli Tutti: A Historical Purview*, for a future world of cooperation, understanding and way of living as individuals and as a society. The Bible is used for reference is *The New Jerusalem Bible*, New York: Doubleday, 1985, referred as NJB.

1. St Francis of Assisi, a Historical Perspective

In this Encyclical seeing St Francis of Assisi as a historical person makes the Christian life plausible and attractive even in the

circumstance of today and at all time. He is the saint of God, humans and the environment. For example, Pope Francis says that St Francis of Assisi was great in the thirteenth century but he has become even more important today (Murphy, 2014). St Francis was considered a saint at the time of his death, October 3, 1226, Francis was canonized only two years later in 1228 by Pope Gregory IX, who said of him on that occasion that Francis shone in his days as a morning star in the midst of clouds (Murphy, 2014). Among those who followed includes St Elizabeth, the young widow of the king of Hungary, who become a secular Franciscan and was renowned for her love of the poor before her early death in 1231- only five years after the death of St Francis himself (Murphy, 2014). It is one of the examples of how greatly was the widespread the spiritual renewal he inspired (Murphy, 2014).

St Francis of Assisi had great influence on the Church of his time. He lived when a time the Church was in a new situation, which needed a renewal. The twelfth century Europe saw the revival of arts and learning. The election of the thirty-seven-year-old noble and learned Innocent III saw the initial establishment of the papal states and an immense enlargement of the papal prestige; Innocent was the first call himself “vicar of Christ” (Murphy, 2014). Innocent III is known for many important reforms in the Church, which has come down to this day although his sponsorship of the Fourth Crusade to liberate the Holy Land from the Muslims proved to be a tragedy, the Pope’s convocation of the Fourth Lateran Council in 1206, was according to John O’Malley, a historian, “one of the largest and most impressive assemblies in the Middle Ages and the largest council in the history of the Church up to that Point,” (Murphy, 2014). It is seen that like the Second Vatican Council, the Fourth Lateran Council of 1215 was a council concerned with reformation (Murphy, 2014). It is reported that it was in this council that created

ever after has called the “Easter duty”: to remain in good standing, all Catholics must receive Holy Communion and, if necessary, go to confession at least once per year (Murphy, 2014).

Apart from the “Easter duty”, Innocent III’s greatest lasting influence upon the Church was his encouragement of the creation of new religious orders by St Dominic and St Francis (Murphy, 2014). Thus, a new body of ministers sprang into being alongside the regular clergy and outside of the conventional parish-based structure (Murphy, 2014). The Dominicans and Franciscans were fundamentally orders of preachers who spoke the Gospel to the people in their own language (Murphy, 2014). Their influence has been felt even today as they grew quickly in this era of renewal, and an amazing seventeen thousand friars of Francis’s new order gathered from all over Europe for the first chapter order in 1260 (Murphy, 2014).

One of the most important and lasting legacy of St Francis is his relationship to “nature” or the environment (Murphy, 2014). For example, the American ecologist Lynn White has written, “the greatest spiritual revolutionary in Western history, St Francis proposed an alternative view of nature and man’s (humans’) relation to it,” (Murphy, 2014). This important characteristic of the saint is confirmed by the Church, when Saint John Paul II in 1980 made him patron saint of ecology (Murphy, 2014). In similar manner the religious historian Marina Warner, speaking for many says, “The Franciscan spirit continues to be considered by agnostics and atheists, as well as believers, as the most genuine expression of Christ’s teaching ever approved by the Vatican,” (Murphy, 2014).

2. St Francis of Assisi and the Gospel

After his encounter with the Lord, St Francis was led by the Gospel way of life was intensely connected to a life of personal prayer, penance, and the witness of charity in the life of the one, who resumed preaching the Gospel (Murphy, 2014). It is said that sometimes Francis saw the duty of prayer as so paramount that he

wondered whether he should take time from prayer to preach at all. It is pointed out that it was only at the urging of Clare and the brothers that he continued to preach to the people the saving message of God (Murphy, 2014). His preaching had such power, and was so challenging to the demons of his time, because he prioritized prayer and embodied witness over preaching (Murphy, 2014). In one occasion St Francis was asked by the bishop to preach to St Clare and the sisters at her convent (Murphy, 2014). St Francis raised his eyes to heaven, where his heart always was, and began to pray to Christ. He then asked to bring ashes to him, and made a circle with them around himself on the pavement, and sprinkled the rest of them on his head (Murphy, 2014). When they waited for him to begin and the blessed father remained standing in silence, no small astonishment arose in their hearts (Murphy, 2014). The saint arose suddenly and to the amazement of the nuns, recited the *Miserere mei Deus* (Psalm 50), in place of a sermon (Murphy, 2014). As soon as he finished he quickly left and the servants of God were so filled with contrition because of the power of this symbolic sermon that their tears flowed in abundance and they could scarcely restrain their hands from inflicting punishment on themselves (Murphy, 2014).

There are many examples of the saint's account of preaching. For example, St Bonaventure speaks of the saint's account of preaching;

It happened that he came to Arezzo at a time when the whole city was shaken by civil war and was on the brink of destruction. Given hospitality in the outskirts, he saw over the city devils rejoicing and inflaming the troubled citizens in mutual slaughter. In order to put to flight those seditious spiritual powers, he sent Brother Sylvester, a man of dove-like simplicity, before him like a herald, saying,

“Go before the gate of the city and on the part of Almighty God command the devils to leave immediately!” This truly obedient man hastened to carry out his father’s orders and, singing psalms of praise before the face of the Lord (Ps 94:2), he began to shout out forcefully before the gate of the city: “On the part of Almighty God and at the command of his servant Francis, depart far from here, all you devils.” At once the city returned to peace and all the citizens reformed their civil statutes very peacefully. Once the raging pride of the devils, which had surrounded the city like a siege, had been driven out, the wisdom of a poor man, namely the humility of Francis, entered in, brought back peace and saved the city. By his lofty virtue of humble obedience, he had gained such powerful control over those rebellious and obstinate spirits that he could repress their ferocious brashness and drive back their savage violence (Murphy, 2014).

Another example is which occurred in 1222, on the Feast of the Assumption, when the saint gathered a crowd in the piazza of the university city of Bologna. Here is an eyewitness account of what had happened;

When I was a student in Bologna, I saw St Francis preach in the main square outside the Palazzo Communale; almost the whole city had gathered to hear him. His theme was “Angels, men and Devils.”

Although no scholar, he spoke so well and developed the subject of these three classes of rational and spiritual beings so clearly that he won the unbounded admiration of even the academics in the crowd. Yet it was more of a general address than a sermon.

He wore a tattered habit, his appearance was insignificant and his face wasn’t handsome, but

God gave his words such power that they actually restored peace to many noble families long torn apart by hatred, cruelty and murder. At the same time ordinary men and women flocked to him out of devotion and respect, afterwards trying to tear a shred from his habit or at least to touch him (Murphy, 2014).

These above passages tell us how relevant is the saint for our world of today, which is marked by so much violence, hatred and cruelty, suffering, hunger and pain, though there is so much progress and understanding among nations and humanity as a whole. Taking the influence of St Francis of Assisi on the Church and the society of his time that Pope Francis brings out his encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* for a better world.

3. Pope Francis and St Francis of Assisi

Cardinal Jorge Mario Bergoglio of Buenos Aires, on March 13, 2013, was elected Pope (Murphy M., 2014). The Pope is the first to come, as he said, “from the edge of the world,” as well as the first Jesuit and the first to take the name Francis (Murphy, 2014). When a Pope is elected to the Pontificate, he selects his name to announce a vision for his pontificate (Murphy M., 2014). It is in this vision that the Pope has taken his name as Francis, after the name of St Francis of Assisi.

In choosing the name when one is elected to the Papacy, every Pope had one’s own choice and preference of one’s mission. Pope John Paul I and Saint John Paul II carried forward the programme of renewal of reform initiated by St John XXIII, who summoned the Second Vatican Council, which was completed by Saint Pope Paul VI (Murphy, 2014). His predecessor Pope Benedict XVI, on the other hand, surveying the increasing secularization of Europe symbolized by the omission of any reference to God in the

European Union’s proposed constitution, selected the name of the great founder of monasticism in the West, Benedict of Nursia, a saint who shaped Western civilization for more than a millennium (Murphy, 2014). In a typical fashion, this is how Pope Francis explains about the selection of his name to a group of six thousand journalists, who had covered the conclave that elected him;

Some people wanted to know why the Bishop of Rome wished to be called Francis. Some thought of Francis Xavier, Francis De Sales, and also Francis of Assisi. I will tell you the story. During the election, I was seated next to the Archbishop Emeritus of Sao Paolo and Prefect Emeritus of the Congregation for the Clergy, Cardinal Claudio Hummes; a good friend, a good friend! When things were looking dangerous, he encouraged me. And when the votes reached two thirds, there was the usual applause, because the Pope had been elected. And he gave me a hug and a kiss, and said: “Don’t forget the poor!” and those words came to me: the poor, the poor. Then, right way, thinking of the poor, I thought of Francis of Assisi. Then I thought of all the wars, as the votes were still being counted, till the end. Francis is also the man of peace. This is how the name came into my heart: Francis of Assisi. For me, he is the man of poverty, the man of peace, the man who loves and protects creation; these days we do not have a very good relationship with creation, do we? He is the man who gives us this spirit of peace, the poor man... How I would like a Church which is poor and for the poor!”(Murphy, 2014).

The Holy Father, Pope Francis during his first Sunday recitation of the Angelus in St Peter’s Square, the Pope added another reason, saying he chose the name of the patron saint of Italy to reinforce “my spiritual link with this land where, as you know, my family has its origins,” (Murphy, 2014). The Pope’s Italian

roots, also emphasized by the selection of this name, reinforce his conception of the Papacy as being fundamentally, the bishop of Rome, who presides in charity over the universal Church. The Holy Father says; “how I would like a Church, which is poor and for the poor!” (Murphy, 2014). What more concise description of Pontificate do we need? Thus the new evangelization, a pastoral priority of the Church in our time, can now be guided-front and centre-by the example of St Francis of Assisi (Murphy, 2014).

Another aspect of the Pope Francis (Jorge Bergoglio) is his humility in being a humble person. He chose his Episcopal motto from the English Church Father Bede, which reads, “*Miserando atque eligendo*” (having pity on him, he chose him). St Bede, who lived in the eighth century, coined this phrase in his exegesis of the call of Matthew to become an apostle (Mt 9:9-13) (Murphy, 2014). St Bede explains that Jesus saw Matthew not just in his appearance and profession but with merciful understanding (Murphy, 2014). The conversion of one sinner gives other sinners an example of repentance and pardon (Murphy, 2014). Bede draws a conclusion; “No sooner was he converted than Matthew drew after him a whole crowd of sinners along the road to salvation (Murphy, 2014). After his election to the Papacy, Pope Francis in the next day in the Sistine Chapel, during the Mass the Holy Father concelebrated with the cardinals who elected him, put aside the prepared Latin homily and speaking spontaneously and standing behind the lectern, he summarized the lectionary’s readings for the day with three verbs: walking, building, and professing (Murphy, 2014).”The thing, however, is not so easy, because in walking, in building and in professing there are sometimes shake-ups,” he said. He continued;

The same Peter, who confessed Jesus Christ says, “You are the Christ, the Son of the living God. I will follow you, but let us not speak of the cross. This has nothing to do with,” he says. “I will follow you in other ways that do not include the cross.” When we walk without the cross, when we build without the cross, and when we profess Christ without the cross, we are not disciples of the Lord. We are worldly; we are bishops, priests, cardinals, popes, but not disciples of the Lord.

I would like that all of us, after these days of grace, might have the courage-the courage-to walk in the presence of the Lord with the cross of the Lord, to build the Church on the blood of the Lord which was shed upon the cross, and to profess the one glory, Christ crucified. In this way the church will go forward (Murphy, 2014).

4. St Francis of Assisi Brings Hope to History

In St Francis, hope was made real, hope entered history, especially via the saint’s contagious care for the poor. It was St Bonaventure, who, along with Thomas of Celano, was one of Francis’s first biographers, summarized *il poverello’s* life and influence this way:

He was poor and lowly, but the Most High God looked upon him with such condescension and kindness that he not only lifted him up in his need from the dust of a worldly life, but made him a practitioner, a leader and a herald of gospel perfection and set him up as a light for believers so that by bearing witness to the light he might prepare for the Lord a way of light and peace into the hearts of the faithful (Murphy, 2014).

Thus, in the person of Pope Francis, St Francis of Assisi exemplifies, in a pre-eminent manner the beauty of the Christian

faith and the joy that comes from believing in it. As Charles M. Murphy points out that its promise is nothing less than the hope of the world at all time. He brings out a poem by Sophecles and translated by Seamus Heaney, where the poet speaks of “a further shore... reachable from here” and a time when “hope and history rhyme,” (Murphy, 2014). It is said that in St Francis of Assisi hope and history actually did come together and memorably ever after, did achieve rhyme (Murphy, 2014).

5. *Fratelli Tutti* of Pope Francis on Fraternity and Social Friendship

In his Encyclical letter *Fratelli Tutti*, Pope Francis reminds us his faithful that saint Francis of Assisi addressed his brothers and sisters and proposed to them a way of life marked by the flavor of the Gospel (Francis, 2021). He says that of the counsels the saint offers the Holy Father selects the one in which he calls for a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance, and declares blessed all those who love their brother “as much when he is far away from him as when he is with him (Murphy, 2014). The Holy Father tells us that saint Francis in his simple and direct way expresses the ‘essence of a fraternal openness’ that allows us to acknowledge, appreciate and love each person, regardless of physical proximity, regardless of where one was born or lives (Francis, 2021).

Pope Francis tells us that St Francis of Assisi who is the saint of fraternal love, simplicity and joy, inspired him to write the Encyclical *Laudato Si'*, prompts him once more to devote this new Encyclical to fraternity and social friendship (Francis, 2021). The Pope says that saint Francis of Assisi felt himself a brother to the sun, the sea and the wind, yet he knew that he was even closer to those of his flesh. He reminds us that saint Francis wherever, he went, sowed seeds of peace

and walked alongside the poor, the abandoned, the infirm and outcast, the least of his brothers and sisters (Francis, 2021).

6. A Saint without Borders

The Pope tells us that there is an episode in the life of saint Francis of Assisi, which reveals the openness of the saint's heart, which knew no bounds and transcends difference of origin, nationality, colour or religion (Francis, 2021). The Holy Father reminds us that the journey undertaken at the time of the Crusades, further demonstrated the breadth and grandeur of St Francis' love, which sought to embrace everyone. He tells us that St Francis' fidelity to his Lord and Master Jesus was commensurate with his love for his brothers and sisters (Francis, 2021). He brings to our awareness that St Francis was unconcerned with the hardships and dangers involved. To show the love of St Francis for everyone the Holy Father tells us that for example, St Francis went to meet the Sultan with same attitude that he instilled in his disciples. St Francis taught his brothers that if they found themselves among the Saracens and other nonbelievers, without renouncing their own identity they were not engage in arguments or disputes, but to be subjected to every human creature for God's sake (Francis, 2021).

a. St Francis of Assisi, a Saint for Our Times

Seeing today's world scenario Pope Francis tells us that in this context of the times, this approach and understanding of a human culture was an extraordinary recommendation. He tells us that we are impressed that some eight hundred years ago Saint Francis urged that all forms of hostility or conflict be avoided and that a humble and fraternal "subjection" be shown to those who did not share his faith (Francis, 2021).

b. St Francis of Assisi was a Person of Empathy

The Holy Father tells us that St Francis was a man of empathy. He did not wage war of words at imposing doctrines. On the other hand, he simply spread the love of God. The Pope reminds us that

he understood that “God is love and those who abide in love abide in God.” (1 Jn 4:16) (Francis, 2021). He exhorts us that in this way, St Francis became a father to all and inspired the vision of a fraternal society, which is very much needed for us humanity today (Francis, 2021). Thus Pope Francis tells us that in the world of that time, bristling with watchtowers and defensive walls, cities were a theatre of brutal wars between powerful families, even as poverty was spreading through the countryside (Francis, 2021). In this scenario of the time of St Francis, the saint was able to welcome true peace into his heart and free himself of the desire to wield power over others. Thus, he became one of the poor and sought to live in harmony with all. The Holy Father tells us that it is St Francis who has inspired these pages.

7. Pope Francis and *Fratelli Tutti*

Drawing inspiration from St Francis of Assisi, Pope Francis writes that issues of human fraternity and social friendship have always been his concern. The Holy Father tells us that in recent years, he has spoken of them repeatedly and in different settings. He says that in this Encyclical, he has sought to bring together many of those statements and to situate them in broader context of reflection and action. For example, the Holy Father reminds us that in the preparation of *Laudato Si'*, he had a source of inspiration in his brother Bartholomew, the Orthodox Patriarch, who has spoken forcefully of our need to care for creation (Francis, 2021). While for this Encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, the Holy Father says that he has felt particularly encouraged by the Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb, with whom he met in Abu Dhabi, where they have declared that “God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters, “ (Francis, 2021). He tells us that this was no mere diplomatic gesture, but a reflection born of dialogue and common commitment. Thus this Encyclical

takes up and develops some of the great themes raised in the Document that they both signed (Francis, 2021). The Holy Father tells us that in this Encyclical, he has also incorporated, along with his own thoughts, a number of letters, documents and considerations that he has received from many individuals and groups throughout the world (Francis, 2021).

a. Fratelli Tutti as an Invitation to Dialogue

By this Encyclical, Pope Francis does not claim to offer a complete teaching on fraternal love, but rather to consider its universal scope, its openness to every man and woman (Francis, 2021). He offers us in this social Encyclical a modest contribution to continued reflection, in the hope that in the face of present-day attempts to eliminate or ignore others, we may prove capable of responding with a new vision of fraternity and social friendship that will not remain at the level of words (Francis, 2021). He tells us that although he has written it from the Christian convictions that inspire and sustain him; he has sought to make this reflection as an invitation to dialogue among all people of good will (Francis, 2021).

b. The Covid-19 Pandemic and *Fratelli Tutti*

The Holy Father tells us that as he was writing this letter, the Covid-19 pandemic unexpectedly erupted, exposing our false securities (Francis, 2021). He writes that aside from the different ways that various countries responded to the crisis, their inability to work together became quite evident (Francis, 2021). He reminds us that for all our hyper-connectivity, we witnessed a fragmentation that made it more difficult to resolve problems that affect us all (Francis, 2021). He tells us that anyone who thinks that the only lesson to be learned was the need to improve what we were already doing, or to refine existing systems and regulations, is denying reality.

c. Purpose of the Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*

The Holy Father tells us that it is his desire that in this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universe aspiration to fraternity, fraternity between all men and women. In this Encyclical we have a splendid secret that shows us how to dream and to turn our life into a wonderful adventure. He reminds us that no one can face life in isolation. We need a community to support and help us, in which we can help one another to keep looking ahead (Francis, 2021). In this Encyclical the Holy Father teaches us the importance of to dream together. While by ourselves, we risk seeing mirages, things that are not there. On the other hand, dreams are built together (Francis, 2021). Thus, the Holy Father exhorts us;

Let us dream, then, as a single human family, as fellow travellers sharing the same flesh, as children of the same earth, which is our common home, each of us bringing the richness of his or her beliefs and convictions, each of us with his or her on voice brothers and sisters all (Francis, 2021).

Conclusion

Thus, seeing the present situation of the world Pope Francis by this Encyclical with the themes, fraternity and social friendship addresses us to build a better, more just and peaceful world, with an emphatic confirmation of a ‘no’ to war and to globalized indifference. He calls it as a social Encyclical, which borrows the title of the “Admonitions,” of St Francis of Assisi, who used these words to address his brothers and sisters. Thus this Encyclical aims to promote a universal aspiration toward fraternity and social friendship to build a better society as one human family and the enhancement and protection of the environment. To have a

fellowship with humanity in similar manner we read in Mark's Gospel:

They came to Capernaum, and when he got into the house he asked them, 'What were you arguing about on the road?' *They said nothing, because on the road they were arguing which of them was the greatest. *So he sat down, called the Twelve to him and said, 'if anyone wants to be first, he must make himself last of all and servant of all.' *He then took a little child who he set among them and embraced, and he said to them, *'Anyone who welcomes a little child such as this in my name, welcomes me; and anyone who welcomes me, welcomes not me but the one who sent me.' (Mk 9:33-37NJB).

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Received: Oct 13, 2021; Accepted: Nov 20, 2021; Words: 5010

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